

Deliverable D1.5

ELIXIR Gender Equality Strategy

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1. Executive Summary

The ELIXIR Gender Equality Strategy is a coordinated initiative to promote gender balance, diversity, and inclusion across the ELIXIR research infrastructure. It builds on the 2018 ELIXIR Equal Opportunities Strategy and aligns with the European Commission's Horizon Europe Gender Equality Plan (2020–2025). This strategy is developed out of ELIXIR-STEERS WP1 and supports excellence in research infrastructure management by embedding inclusive practices.

Key Components of the Strategy

- Data-Driven Foundations - two complementary approaches informed the strategy:
 - A desk analysis of gender distribution across ELIXIR Nodes and roles (259 individuals).
 - An Equality, Diversity, and Inclusion (EDI) perception survey (58 responses from 22 Nodes) using content from the GEAM¹ tool to assess perceived barriers and opportunities.
- Findings:
 - Female representation in Nodes sits at 35% overall; only 31% in leadership roles (e.g. Heads of Node).
 - Countries with strong female participation in leadership roles are Portugal (71%), Sweden (64%), and Estonia (56%) suggesting positive local conditions or successful gender initiatives.
 - Countries with less than 25% female representation across all roles include Slovenia, Hungary, Czech Republic, Luxembourg, and Israel. However, these numbers should be approached with caution since reasons behind them could vary from size of a country, and/or bioinformatics community, maturity of a Node, etc.
 - Certain leadership roles (e.g., Training Coordinator) have strong female presence, while other leadership roles that are perceived to be technical show sharp underrepresentation (e.g., 9% Technical Coordinators are women).
 - Key barriers to participation include time pressure (67%), caring responsibilities, limited institutional support, and lack of visibility of opportunities.
 - While 76% of respondents agree ELIXIR promotes gender equality, only 50% feel men and women are treated equally, and access to senior roles remains skewed.
 - Disparity in gender of respondents to survey, with females accounting for 71% and males 28%.
- Cultural & Structural Gaps:
 - Female underrepresentation in technical and leadership roles persists.
 - Remote work is valued as a tool for equality, especially by caregivers and those with health constraints.
 - Visual representation and communication could better reflect diversity beyond gender, including race, LGBTQ+ identities, age, and socio-economic background.

¹ <https://act-on-gender.eu/nes/gender-equality-audit-and-monitoring-geam-tool>

- Psychological safety and trust in EDI reporting mechanisms need improvement.

Strategic priorities and targets

1. Increase female leadership² to $\geq 40\%$ across all ELIXIR roles by 2027.
2. Address country-level disparities: reduce the number of countries with $< 25\%$ female engagement by half.
3. Double female representation in technical roles (e.g. Technical Coordinator, Platform lead).
4. Sustain strong female presence in mid-level roles.
5. Encourage overall female representation in the leading roles in ELIXIR Nodes.
6. Mitigate functional silos where women are concentrated in support roles (e.g. Head of Nodes vs Node Coordinators roles); reduce roles with 0% female representation (e.g. Technical Coordinators) to zero.
7. Increase future EDI Perceptions survey participation amongst males from 28% $\rightarrow \geq 40\%$.

Recommendations and actions

- Conduct biannual monitoring of gender-disaggregated data by role and Node.
- Implement Node-level action plans for underperforming areas.
- Share best practices and success stories from institutions/Nodes.
- Showcase and scale best practices from exemplary Nodes. Promote recognition of such achievements at the European level (e.g. via the EU Award for Gender Equality Champions).³
- Encourage inclusive recruitment, flexible work arrangements, and better support for parental leave and carers.
- Improve communication, mentoring, and leadership development pathways (e.g. ELEAD 2.0).
- Repeat the EDI survey in regular agreed cycles (e.g. annually, bi-annually, ELIXIR Scientific Programme related) to track progress.

ELIXIR has taken meaningful steps to advance gender equality, but significant challenges remain—especially regarding female leadership, female participation in technical roles, and addressing countries with overall low female representation. Sustained, data-informed actions and institutional accountability will be essential to achieving equitable participation and inclusive excellence across the ELIXIR community.

² The term 'leadership' in this context refers to roles with an ELIXIR public recognition in the node page, and with specific responsibilities within ELIXIR, e.g. Head of Node, Deputy Head of Node, Node Coordinator, Training Coordinator, Technical Coordinator.

³https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/funding/funding-opportunities/prizes/eu-award-gender-equality-champions_en

2. Contribution toward project objectives

With this deliverable, the project has reached or the deliverable has contributed to the following objectives/key results:

Objective no. / Key Result no. Description	Contributed to:
Objective 1: Partner with user communities to create a toolkit for robust, reproducible, and green software and workflows that allow life-scientists to benefit from open science practices in the emerging European federated data landscape. (WP2, WP3, WP4, WP5)	
<u>Key Result 1.1:</u> Established partnerships with user communities that capture experiences and embed these in good practices for robust, reproducible, and green software and workflows (WP2)	No
<u>Key Result 1.2:</u> A toolkit developed consisting of guidelines, best practices and services that supports software development and recognition of individuals involved in software development (WP2, WP3)	No
<u>Key Result 1.3:</u> Community-wide agreement on key indicators for technical, scientific, and environmental benchmarking (WP2) embedded into established software and workflow benchmarking systems (WP3)	No
<u>Key Result 1.4:</u> Practices for robust, reproducible, and green software and workflows (WP2, WP3) are adopted and embedded in ELIXIR Nodes (WP4), supporting the European federated data landscape and Horizon Europe projects	No
<u>Key Result 1.5:</u> Demonstration of the greening potential and reduced carbon footprint of software best practice by applying toolkit and indicators in community-driven activities (WP2)	No
<u>Key Result 1.6:</u> Stimulate engagement and uptake by users via European and national communication and outreach programmes (WP5)	No
Objective 2: Enable the landscape for cross-border data analysis in the life sciences by embedding common practice across the whole European Research Area via effective national ELIXIR Nodes. (WP4, WP5)	
<u>Key Result 2.1:</u> Build a common toolkit to enhance the operational and managerial capacity of ELIXIR Nodes that comprise all aspects of sustainability (operational excellence, business planning, interactions with industry and impact assessment) (WP4, WP5)	No
<u>Key Result 2.2:</u> Expand the ELIXIR's Membership by transitioning candidate countries into fully operational national Nodes using capacity building actions (WP4, WP5)	No

<u>Key Result 2.3:</u> Strengthen excellence in RI management with an ELIXIR training programme that complements established Europe-wide offerings with the infrastructure specific needs (WP4)	Yes
<u>Key Result 2.4:</u> Strengthen the capacity of national training programmes (WP4) to scale the dissemination, training, and uptake of the ELIXIR software development toolkit for robust, reproducible, and green software and workflows (WP5)	Yes
<u>Key Result 2.5:</u> Work with funders to embed the practice in data and software management plans in guidelines to grantees (WP5)	No
Objective 3: Partner in Europe and internationally for global competitiveness and sustainability. (WP5)	
<u>Key Result 3.1:</u> Development of national SME and industry partnerships to support the European innovation ecosystem (WP5)	No
<u>Key Result 3.2:</u> Partnerships with other ESFRI RIs to strengthen the wider RI landscape (WP5) and support adoption of robust, reproducible, and green workflows across RI facilities.	No
<u>Key Result 3.3:</u> Foster global knowledge-exchange to drive good international practices and embed international partnerships in Node activities (WP5)	No
<u>Key Result 3.4:</u> Deliver a Node dissemination and communications toolkit that enables ELIXIR Nodes to amplify engagement with scientists and other stakeholders (WP5)	No

3. Introduction

ELIXIR is a European life sciences infrastructure, bringing together scientists from 21 Member countries, three Observer countries and EMBL-EBI. The additional complexity of ELIXIR's structure lies with its coordination Hub being hosted by EMBL-EBI, thus following EMBL's policies, and over 240 research institutes representing 22 ELIXIR Nodes following their own institutional policies.

The work reported in this deliverable is part of the efforts invested in WP1: Coordination and Support and its Task 1.5: Excellence in Management of the ELIXIR STEERS project. The overall aim of the task is to continue to build capacity in management across the ELIXIR Nodes. It is conducted in close collaboration with WP4: Strengthening and equipping ELIXIR Nodes and Node staff with key skills and resources in organisation, management and training, in alignment with a number of internally funded ELIXIR projects (Commissioned Services) and initiatives relevant for the topic.

While WP1 addresses broad themes such as strengthening executive management capacity across ELIXIR Nodes, enhancing Node coordination and fostering grant management expertise, deliverable **D1.5: Gender Equality Strategy** focuses specifically on scaling up the implementation of the *ELIXIR Equal Opportunities Strategy*, providing a framework for adopting and strengthening EC's Horizon Europe Gender Equality Plan (part of the EC Gender Equality Strategy 2020-2025).

The ELIXIR Equal Opportunities Strategy, published in 2018⁴, outlined key challenges related to inequality in science, academia, and research infrastructures, highlighting the persistent underrepresentation of women and minority groups, particularly in senior academic and leadership roles. In response, ELIXIR took proactive steps to address this: gender balance is required in appointments to governance structures, gender diversity is a consideration for selection of speakers at events, and a comprehensive Code of Conduct for Events was introduced.

The current ELIXIR Scientific Programme (2024-2028) places a strong emphasis on supporting both Node development and the growth of people within the ELIXIR community. This work began in the previous Scientific Programme (2019-2023), in particular through activities led by ELIXIR Spain with 'Bioinfo4Women'⁵ initiative, and the ELIXIR LEadership And Diversity mentoring programme - ELEAD Pilot (led by ELIXIR Spain and ELIXIR Germany). The ELIXIR Scientific Programme 2024-2028 has seen the successful pilot turned into a full fledged ELEAD 2nd Edition supporting mentorship and peer support among women in middle-level management roles, as well as expert training on leadership skills. Complimentary activities in the People Pulse project⁶ are aimed at developing ELIXIR experts in general for efficient operations and management as part of the distributed research infrastructure.

The work described in this Deliverable was conducted through two parallel processes: 1) a desk analysis to describe the current available data about gender balance across the pan-European ELIXIR community and roles participants from ELIXIR Nodes hold in the infrastructure, and 2) a gender

⁴Gater C. ELIXIR Equal Opportunities Strategy [version 1; not peer reviewed]. F1000Research 2018, 7(ELIXIR):1234 (document) (<https://doi.org/10.7490/f1000research.1115874.1>)

⁵<https://bioinfo4women.bsc.es/>

⁶<https://elixir-europe.org/internal-projects/people>

equality perception survey seeking insight on perceptions of equality and representation, as well as diversity across the ELIXIR network. In particular, the survey asked for feedback on issues that may impact gender equality, leading to better understanding of equality in the broader context of socio-demographic and identity factors such as age, ethnicity, marital status and religion. Alongside desk analysis of ELIXIR roles, the survey informed the deliverable D1.5 describing an ELIXIR Gender Equality Strategy addressing the Horizon Europe Gender Equality Plan (GEP) requirements and EC gender dimensions considerations, and provides a framework for adopting these within the ELIXIR network.

4. Description of work accomplished

4.1 Desk analysis

The desk analysis, conducted over the period of December 2024 - May 2025, aimed to explore gender balance across the ELIXIR community by examining gender distribution per role. The analysis sought to capture the complexity of the issue, explain the observed results, and guide future actions to maintain or improve the balance. The data about Nodes was taken from ELIXIR Hub internal records. A total of 259 individuals performing in ELIXIR roles were represented in the desk analysis, including:

- Administrator,
- Head of Node,
- Deputy Head of Node,
- Community Lead,
- Contract Administrator,
- Commissioned Services project lead,
- Data Stewardship Manager,
- Platform Lead (ExCo),
- Training Coordinator (TrC),
- Deputy Training Coordinator,
- Technical Coordinator (TeC),
- Deputy Technical Coordinator,
- Node Coordinator (NoC),
- Deputy Node Coordinator,
- Finances,
- Legal,
- Research Data Management Coordinator,
- Research Office,

These roles reflect key positions across ELIXIR and served as the basis for the gender distribution analysis.

4.2 Survey of Equality, Diversity and Inclusion perceptions in ELIXIR

The gender equality perceptions' survey was conducted in the period from 9 June to 14 July 2025, gathering a total of 58 responses across ELIXIR's 22 Nodes and their member institutions. The survey was conducted using the Jisc Online Survey tool due to feasibility related to data protection policies for EMBL and ELIXIR. However, the majority of questions were pre-prepared from the Gender Equality Audit and Monitoring (GEAM) tool, which is a survey-based platform used for conducting gender equality audits within organizations, particularly in the context of Gender Equality Plans (GEPs). It was initially developed in the ACT project (<https://project-act.eu/>) and has since been deployed in over 50 organizations across Europe. The tool helps identify disparities, track progress, and implement effective policies related to gender equality. There are several reasons for choosing to administer the survey developed and embedded in the GEAM tool:

- It is used to assess the effectiveness of GEPs by measuring changes in employee perceptions and experiences over time.
- It helps identify areas where GEPs may be lacking or where further action is needed.
- The data collected through GEAM can inform the development and refinement of existing GEPs.

For the purpose of D1.5, the GEAM survey proved to be a valuable resource informing the improvement of gender equality, providing a data-driven approach to understanding and addressing gender-related issues within ELIXIR infrastructure.

The survey had 20 questions in total, including multiple choice, and open ended questions format. It takes approximately 30 minutes to complete the survey. The survey consists of several parts related to different topics:

- Individual information
- Current position
- Perceptions of equality, diversity and inclusion
- Work-life balance:
 - Caring responsibilities
 - Flexible / remote working
 - Parental leave
- ELIXIR Culture and Climate - Gender Equality:
 - Recruitment
 - Promotion
 - Formal training and career development opportunities
 - Invitations or opportunities (i.e. funding, additional time) to attend conferences, lectures, etc.
 - Recognition of intellectual contributions during meetings, conferences, workshops, etc.
 - Awards and recognition of excellence
 - Support in grant preparation and writing
- Experiences or perceptions of gender bias (or lack thereof) in ELIXIR (open ended question)

Results obtained from the desk analysis as well as submitted responses from the survey are analysed in more detail under the next section.

5. Results

5.1 Desk analysis results

Out of the 259 individuals from ELIXIR Nodes who are performing a specific role for which data is available in ELIXIR, 102 (or approximately 39%) are female (F), and 157 (or approximately 61%) are male (M). The initial percentages suggest an overall imbalance, however, further breakdown per country, role and Node reveals more specific details on some Nodes' gender representation when it comes to engagement in ELIXIR activities.

The gender distribution of ELIXIR roles across 22 ELIXIR Nodes is visible in graph 1 below.

ELIXIR Nodes Gender Distribution

Graph 1: Gender distribution of ELIXIR roles across ELIXIR Nodes

5.1.1 Gender distribution of ELIXIR roles across ELIXIR Nodes

Female engagement <30%

Further analysis revealed significant imbalances in regards to the female versus male participation in ELIXIR activities and roles on the country level. Namely, there are several countries whose data suggests female engagement of less than 30, however caution is advised with interpretation due to

small sample size. These countries may benefit from priority attention and gender equality initiatives. The following countries fall into that category:

- Slovenia: 20% female participation,
- Czech Republic: 23%,
- Luxembourg: 22%,
- Israel: 25%.

Germany has the highest total number of female participation in leading roles, but also a stark gender imbalance with women comprising approximately 32% of the population engaged in ELIXIR activities.

Female engagement 40-50%

There are a number of countries with near-parity, showcasing almost equal engagement of female and male participants in ELIXIR activities. These countries could serve as benchmarks for gender parity. Their national and institutional strategies may be scalable.

- France (47%)
- Greece (44%)
- Norway (44%)
- UK (46%)
- Finland (40%)
- Denmark (40%)
- Ireland (40%)

Female engagement $\geq 50\%$

Countries with high Female representation across ELIXIR activities and roles are presented below. These are potential case studies or champions for best practices in gender balance, though it is also important to note the small sample size for some.

- Portugal (71%)⁷
- Sweden (64%)
- Estonia (100%)⁸
- Belgium (50%)

5.1.2 Gender distribution across ELIXIR roles

The dataset examined covers 259 individuals across a range of organisational roles. In general, ELIXIR roles are performed by 102 female participants (or approximately 39%), and 157 male participants (or approximately 61%). The gender distribution across ELIXIR roles is visible in graph 2 below.

⁷ low overall count

⁸ low overall count

ELIXIR Per Role Gender Distribution

Graph 2: Gender distribution across ELIXIR roles

Roles with high Female representation

There are certain roles within ELIXIR that traditionally foster high female participation. These roles demonstrate strong female representation and could be leveraged to promote internal leadership development. They are listed below:

- Training Coordinator (TrC): 58% female
- Deputy Training Coordinator (TrC): 80% female
- Legal roles: 67% female
- Unspecified role: 83% female⁹

Although roles such as Head of Node and Platform Lead include women, their representation as suggested by analysis (~31%) remains low, suggesting a glass ceiling in access to lead roles (e.g. roles with an ELIXIR public recognition and with specific responsibilities within ELIXIR, e.g. Head of Node, Deputy Head of Node, Node Coordinator, Training Coordinator, Technical Coordinator).

Due to the exploratory nature of this exercise, no further disambiguation was carried out to assign specific roles within the “Unspecified role” group. Addressing this gap by ensuring clearer role specification will be an important focus in future iterations of the ELIXIR Gender Equality Plan.

Roles with mid-range Female representation (30–45%)

⁹ Greek and Finish Node

Moderate representation of females can be found in governance roles, some surpassing the overall moderate ratings suggested by analysis below for majority of those role; the position of Node Coordinator is held by far more women than men across ELIXIR Nodes, while there is still quite visible under-representation of female role holders in relation to the Head of Node (31%) and Commissioned Services projects (CoS) leads (38%) positions. However, Deputy positions (although not mandatory) are almost at parity (45%) across ELIXIR Nodes.

- Head of Node: 31% female
- Commissioned Services leads (CoS): 38% female
- Deputy Head of Node: 45% female
- Node Coordinator: 65% female (*above parity*)

Roles with low Female representation

Finally, there are critical technical or strategic roles where female representation is nearly absent, highlighting an area for strong focused improvement, and even targeted actions to increase the involvement of women and reduce the effect of stereotypes (including conscious and unconscious bias) often still present in selection processes. These are the following roles:

- Technical Coordinator (TeC): 9% female
- Deputy Technical Coordinator (TeC): 8% female

The stark gender imbalance in technical (TeC) coordination roles in general underscores the need for gender-sensitive recruitment, training, and mentoring related to those positions.

5.2 Survey of Equality, Diversity and Inclusion perceptions in ELIXIR - results

5.2.1 Individual information

The first part of the survey was dedicated to general anonymised information about participants (their age and gender identity). These questions help us understand if perceptions of equality, diversity and inclusion vary across different social groups. Results presented in Graph 3 below reveal the age structure of our respondents' sample: the most represented age categories in this survey are those from 30-40 years of age (34%) and 41-50 years of age (31%), followed by the 50+ category with 19% of respondents. Early career respondents form 12% of the sample, and 61+ are represented by 3% of respondents in our sample.

Graph 3: Age categories of survey respondents

The majority of respondents (71%) identified as female, and 28% identified as male, while the remaining 2% identified as non-binary.

5.2.2 Current position

In this section of the survey, participants were asked to provide more details about the **area of institutional engagement and role** alongside their participation in ELIXIR. The following areas of engagement were reported by survey respondents:

- Bioinformatics - 34%
- Data Management - 40%
- Communications - 24%
- Community Management - 14%
- External Relations - 16%
- IT Operations - 7%
- Legal/ethical - 5%
- Operations/Administration/HR - 10%
- Project Management - 59%
- Research Support - 5%

- Software Development - 9%
- Training - 33%
- Other (reported as roles in Management, Research, and Data Stewardship) - 10%

With regards to **seniority level** in their current position, roughly half of survey respondents (53%) belong to the middle level of seniority (e.g. Manager/Team leader/Assistant Professor). The next most populated category of respondents (29%) is the early career level (e.g. officer/technician, PhD candidate, Postdoc). Senior positions (e.g. Director, Associate/Full Professor) are occupied by 14% of respondents.

Seniority levels

Graph 4: Seniority of positions according to gender

Regarding their role in ELIXIR, participants were asked about **activities they were currently involved with** in the ELIXIR context. The answers are summarised in Graph 4 below:

Graph 5: Involvement of survey respondents in ELIXIR activities

Majority of respondents (66%) have been involved in ELIXIR internal projects (Commissioned Services), however, the second highest category is participation in ELIXIR enabled or coordinated EC grants (57%). When it comes to ELIXIR's scientific and technical groups (Communities and Platforms), almost half of respondents are active in both, followed by more informal engagement with ELIXIR as in e.g. Focus groups (41%). Finally, 40% of our respondents also engage in governance and coordination of their Nodes.

The next question required respondents' opinion on whether **participation in ELIXIR helped or hindered their career progression in any way**. Visual representation of answers is captured in Graph 6 below.

Given the open ended type of question, the responses are summarised below for the clearer overview. 30 positive responses (78.9%) were received in total. These responses clearly state that ELIXIR helped their career in multiple and following ways:

- Networking, visibility, and recognition,
- Skill development and training,
- Promotion and leadership opportunities,
- Broader perspectives and professional growth.

Following responses (6 in total, or 15.8%) mentioned some positive aspects, but included caveats such as:

- Only helped a little,

- Benefits mainly in the past, now more draining,
- Helped with network, but unclear impact on career progression,
- Helped within ELIXIR but not in their own organization.

Finally, 2 negative responses (5.3%) were received suggesting no benefit and/or possible hindrance to the career progression, but offered no specific details or more context.

Graph 6: Career progression and ELIXIR participation

With regards to respondents' **access to training or development resources** and opportunities provided directly or indirectly by ELIXIR, the following answers were received and have been presented in Graph 5 below.

The majority of respondents (60+ %) have utilised benefits provided by participation in ELIXIR's flagship events (All Hands Meeting, Biohackathon), as well as conferences and other events sponsored and/or organised by ELIXIR.

These were followed by respondents' access to ELIXIR's Staff Exchange and Travel grants funding instruments (with ca. 30+%), as well as access to various training courses provided by ELIXIR.

Furthermore, access to mentoring activities was mentioned, in particular through the ELEAD internal project (26%).

The remaining 15% of respondents reported different access opportunities, e.g. to knowledge exchange clubs (e.g. TeSS) or Knowledge Exchange funding instruments focusing on Nodes collaboration with industry partners. Some reported no access to any of the offered resources to choose from (10%). Final 3% mentioned other opportunities for training and development such as ELIXIR communities activities and tools and resources at Nodes' disposal, as well as coordination activities and meetings (Node, Training and Technical).

Graph 7: Access to ELIXIR training and development opportunities

When asked about their opinion regarding certain criteria to be a **barrier to accessing ELIXIR opportunities and activities**, the vast majority of respondents (67%) stated time pressure as the most important cause. It is followed by cost stated as a reason with 34% of respondents concurring. Between 15% and 25% of respondents named several other reasons preventing them to have full access to opportunities and activities offered by ELIXIR, namely:

- Parenting/caring responsibilities (24%),
- Location (22%),
- Lack of support from management (17%),
- Training not meeting their needs (16%).

Finally, 5% to 10% of respondents stated the following reasons as barriers to ELIXIR opportunities and work:

- None of the above (10%),
- Other - please specify (10%)*
- Long-term health condition or disability (5%),
- Language (5%).

*Responses received under the 'Other' category are summarised below:

1. Information overload & lack of structure

- Too much training material, poorly categorised and hard to navigate.
2. Short-term focus of ELIXIR
 - Limited long-term planning; some felt the short project cycles made participation harder to sustain.
 3. Institutional constraints
 - Need for internal approval; ELIXIR participation not always prioritized by home institutions.
 4. Inflexibility for early-career researchers
 - Advanced planning requirements conflict with short contracts; late-joiners are often excluded from major events (e.g. All Hands Meeting).
 5. Unclear communication
 - Lack of visibility or clarity about available opportunities and unclear communication channels.

5.2.3 Perceptions of equality, diversity and inclusion

In this section, the focus was on better understanding the various socio-demographic factors that may influence equality and access within ELIXIR.

The respondents were asked to indicate whether any of the identified factors appear to affect equitable access to opportunities in their ELIXIR-related work or environment (e.g. to be appointed in ELIXIR role at their institution, to access training, knowledge exchange or mentoring provided by ELIXIR, the possibility to receive funding to support ELIXIR activities, etc.). Answers have been summarised in Table 1 below:

Table 1: Factors influencing equitable access to opportunities in ELIXIR

Factor	Yes	No	Sometimes	Not sure
1. Age	18%	54%	19%	9%
2. Caring responsibilities	19%	32%	18%	32%
3. Disability	11%	44%	11%	35%
4. Ethnicity	7%	60%	9%	24%
5. Gender identity	11%	61%	18%	11%
6. Marital or partnership status	4%	74%	2%	21%
7. Nationality	11%	65%	9%	16%
8. Pregnancy, maternity and parental leave	18%	39%	14%	30%
9. Race	7%	60%	5%	28%

10. Religion or belief	0%	69%	9%	22
11. Sex (biological)	16%	65%	12%	7%
12. Sexual orientation	4%	74%	9%	14%
13. Socio-economic background	7%	65%	12%	16%
14. Trans-identity/history	5%	61%	7%	27%

All the factors that more than 60% of respondents suggested don't influence equitable access to opportunities in ELIXIR were marked bold. That leaves four factors with more attention and detail needed for conclusive results:

- **Age:** although approximately half of respondents reported no problems due to their age, ca. 20%, or every fifth person engaged in ELIXIR, reports either having problems with access to opportunities and activities due to their age or having access difficulties occasionally. In particular, while 46% of **respondents under 40** thinks that age doesn't play a role in hindering their access to equitable opportunities in ELIXIR (38% no, 8% not sure), 54% combined (31% yes, 23% sometimes) has indicated they do think that's the case either occasionally or on regular basis. Vast majority of **respondents over 40** (68%) indicated that age has no influence on access to equal opportunities in ELIXIR, with 10% not sure, and combined 22% (6% yes, 16% sometimes) perceives that occasionally and seldom age does play a role in access.
 - When filtered for **female only point of view**, a significant majority of female respondents (55%) did not perceive age as influencing equal access or opportunities within ELIXIR. However, 43% combined (Yes + Sometimes) did indicate some level of perceived impact, which suggests age-related dynamics may still be a concern for a notable minority.
 - Filtered for **male only point of view**, results suggest that male respondents (56%) did not believe age influences equal opportunity in ELIXIR. However, 44% (Yes, Sometimes, or Not Sure) showed some degree of concern or uncertainty, indicating that for some, age may still be perceived as a potential factor.
- **Caring responsibilities:** similar to age factor, ca. 20% of respondents had experienced less accessibility (regularly or occasionally) to opportunities offered by ELIXIR due to their caring responsibilities.
 - When filtered for **female only point of view**, the results show a relatively even distribution of views. 44% of respondents (Yes + Sometimes) indicated that caring responsibilities do or can influence equal opportunities, while only 28% rejected this notion outright. The high number of "Not sure" responses (27%) suggests uncertainty or lack of visibility into how this characteristic plays out in the organisation.

- According to **male only point of view** on caring responsibilities factor, responses are more spread out. Only a small group (7%) directly sees this as a factor, while 26% (Yes + Sometimes) perceive some impact. The high “Not sure” response (40%) suggests many male respondents may not have full visibility or personal experience with how caring responsibilities intersect with opportunity in ELIXIR.
- Disability: while ca. 10% of respondents have difficulties (regularly or occasionally) accessing ELIXIR opportunities and activities due to their disability, around 35% are not sure of the answer.
 - While filtered for **female only point of view** results show a minority (13%) responses indicating “Yes,” a large share of respondents expressed uncertainty (35%) or conditional influence (15% Sometimes). This might suggest that disability issues may not be openly visible or discussed, or that their impact on access is not uniformly experienced.
 - There is no direct perception of disability as an influencing factor among the **male respondents**. Still, the 38% “Not sure” shows some level of uncertainty, perhaps indicating lack of exposure or clarity on this issue.
- Pregnancy, maternity and parental leave: similar to age and caring responsibilities, ca. 20% of respondents had experienced less accessibility to opportunities offered by ELIXIR due to their pregnancy, maternity and parental leave from work. 15% occasionally feel deprived of those opportunities, while 30% remain undecided.
 - Filtered according to gender (**female**) this category had the highest “Yes” response (25%) among the four, highlighting that pregnancy and parental leave are seen by a quarter of female respondents as directly influencing opportunities. An additional 13% noted “Sometimes,” while 28% were unsure – reinforcing the notion that family-related leave may still carry perceived career implications in the ELIXIR environment.
 - Half the **male respondents** (50%) said this factor does not influence opportunity, but a combined 50% (Sometimes + Not Sure) either perceive potential influence or are uncertain. This could reflect indirect awareness of potential career impacts, especially regarding female colleagues.

The results on four factors discussed above were filtered by gender are presented in Tables 1.1 and 1.2 below:

Table 1.1 Several factors influencing equitable access to opportunities in ELIXIR - female perspective

Factor	Yes	No	Sometimes	Not sure
Age	18%	55%	25%	3%
Caring responsibilities	24%	28%	20%	27%
Disability	13%	38%	15%	35%
Pregnancy, maternity and parental leave	25%	35%	13%	28%

Table 1.2 Several factors influencing equitable access to opportunities in ELIXIR - male perspective

Factor	Yes	No	Sometimes	Not sure
Age	13%	56%	6%	25%
Caring responsibilities	7%	40%	13%	40%
Disability	0%	63%	0%	38%
Pregnancy, maternity and parental leave	0%	50%	19%	31%

The gender-filtered results demonstrate several trends (summary of comparison is presented in Table 1.3 below):

- Female respondents consistently report a higher perception of influence for all four factors.
- Male respondents express more uncertainty, particularly around caring responsibilities and pregnancy/maternity leave.
- Disability is more likely to be seen as a non-issue by men (0% said “Yes”) but carries more perceived impact or uncertainty among women.

Table 1.3 Summary comparison by gender regarding several factors influencing equitable access to opportunities in ELIXIR

Factor	Yes (♀/♂)	No (♀/♂)	Sometimes (♀/♂)	Not Sure (♀/♂)
Age	18% / 13%	55% / 56%	25% / 6%	3% / 25%
Caring responsibilities	24% / 7%	28% / 40%	20% / 13%	27% / 40%
Disability	13% / 0%	38% / 63%	15% / 0%	35% / 38%
Pregnancy, maternity and parental leave	25% / 0%	35% / 50%	13% / 19%	28% / 31%

The following question aimed to inquire which of the above factors needed to be **better represented in ELIXIR visual communications**. In total, 27 answers were provided. Given the open ended type of question, the responses are summarised below for the clearer overview:

Overall insight

The majority of responses do not express strong dissatisfaction, but over half (14+) show a desire for broader and deeper representation, especially around race, LGBTQ+, age, and parental roles. Only a quarter of respondents were clearly satisfied or indifferent, while others were cautiously supportive or neutral. There's an opportunity for ELIXIR to strengthen its visual inclusivity by addressing less-visible and less-represented characteristics.

Seven respondents had no concerns regarding the visual representation of factors influencing accessibility to ELIXIR activities and opportunities. Respondents in this group expressed that:

- ELIXIR is already doing a good job in its visual communications.
- No underrepresentation was noticed.
- Diversity is seen as adequately showcased, or not relevant to visual communications.
- Some noted limited local relevance (e.g. in small or homogeneous Nodes) or insufficient evidence to judge.

Eight respondents expressed moderate concerns with the following suggestions:

- Recognised existing diversity efforts (e.g. ELEAD, gender representation).
- Pointed out gaps in representing characteristics such as age, nationality, parental status, and technical work packages.
- Recommended more inclusive campaigns for young researchers, parents, and minorities.
- Called for representation that reflects the true diversity of ELIXIR's people.

Finally, the last six respondents offered a more critical approach and identified several areas of improvement. These respondents clearly felt ELIXIR’s visual communications are:

- Still overwhelmingly white, male, and cisgender.
- Too focused on gender, neglecting LGBTQ+, race, and intersectionality.
- At risk of coming across as “neutral” to the point of being uncaring.
- In need of bolder efforts to demonstrate inclusivity in imagery and messaging.

Caring responsibilities

Over several questions the survey inquired in more detail about conditions surrounding caring responsibilities across the ELIXIR community. The answers are presented in Table 2 below:

Table 2: Caring responsibilities - status in ELIXIR community

Question	Yes	No	Prefer not to say
Are you the primary carer or assistant for an adult requiring care?	7%	91%	2%
Are you the parent or legal guardian of any children below 18 years old?	43%	57%	0%

Regarding respondents’ demographics by age, the majority of women fall into the age group of 31-50 years old, while the majority of male respondents belong to the 41-60 age group. Female respondents skew younger than male respondents, with a greater concentration in the 31–50 age group, while a higher proportion of men are in the 51–60 age group.

In addition, when filtered by gender, a slightly higher proportion of men report being adult carers compared to women (13% vs. 5%), while a higher proportion of female respondents are parents/guardians of children under 18 compared to male respondents (49% vs. 31%).

When asked about sharing the care responsibilities with another adult, and in what capacity, the following answers were offered:

- No, I’m a single parent/legal guardian (4%),
- Yes, care responsibilities are equally shared (72%),
- Yes, I am primarily responsible (20%),
- Yes, I do not have primary responsibility (4%).

Women are more likely to report being primarily responsible for childcare (25%) or being a single parent (5%), while no men reported being either. Men report either equal sharing (80%) or not having primary responsibility (20%).

Flexible / remote working

Over several questions the survey inquired in more detail about respondents' experience considering work arrangements at their current workplace over the last 12 months. When asked whether they worked from home or other places that were not their office, the following answers were given:

- Yes, I exclusively work remotely (9%),
- Yes, hybrid working arrangement (79%),
- No (10%),
- Prefer not to say (2%).

However, if answered Yes, more options were displayed leading to the following summary of answers presented in Graph 6 below. The majority of respondents (63%) stated they could better concentrate at home. 30% to 50% of respondents argued that remote working arrangements allowed them to more easily deal with domestic duties, arrange work outside of office hours, and deal with social commitments/leisure or take care of their children.

The rest of respondents (below 30%) stated that it was easier to take care of friends and relatives, or they were requested to work remotely by their employer.

Graph 8: Reasons for remote working arrangements

However, 27% of respondents offered other reasons, summarised below.

Several respondents offered positive and/or productivity-driven responses. These responses frame remote work as a strategic choice that enhances efficiency or productivity, and these respondents see remote work as a proactive, productive decision that improves time use and work flow:

- Avoiding commuting to save time and energy.
- Improved task management and focus.
- Better alignment with work needs.

Another group of respondents offered more neutral/situational or practical reasons. These reasons reflect practical realities or organisational constraints that make remote work a convenient or necessary compromise, rather than a strong preference. They describe logistical barriers or local policies that lead to working remotely; not driven by strong preferences, but by circumstance.

- Distance from workplace.
- Institutional limitations.
- Appointments or schedule conflicts.

Several responses highlighted physical and mental health as central motivations for remote work. These responses underscore that remote work supports wellbeing, offering flexibility for those managing health challenges, both physical and mental:

- Chronic illness or physical limitations.
- Mental health or emotional strain.

Parental leave

The respondents were asked whether they are currently taking any form of parental leave or have they done so in the last 5 years. Parental leave includes maternity leave, paternity leave, adoption leave, unpaid- or paid parental leave. Given that 27 respondents provided answers to this question, it is assumed that only the ones with children did it. The following answers were given:

- Yes (19%),
- No (81%),
- Prefer not to say (0%).

The respondents were further asked to describe their perceptions of the uptake and use of parental leave options and resources, such as working part-time or taking extended unpaid parental leave, in their organisation. In total, 26 responses have been provided. Given the open ended nature of the question, the responses have been grouped from positive to negative, based on sentiment and perceived effectiveness of parental leave policies and experiences:

Overall insight

Parental leave is generally supported, but implementation and culture vary widely. There are structural and social gaps, particularly around: support for returning parents, part-time work stigma, and gender-based assumptions. In addition, unpaid or extended leave is rarely used, often for economic reasons. Positive examples exist, especially in institutions with flexible policies and proactive cultural support.

Several respondents offered positive perceptions of parental leave. These respondents shared favourable views of how parental leave is handled in their organisation:

- Parental leave options are seen as flexible, supported, and accessible, including part-time and fully paid leave.
- Organisations are perceived as attentive to family responsibilities and supportive of work-life balance.
- Some highlighted compliance with national legislation and fair treatment in practice.
- Recognition of improvements like gradual return for mothers and flexible hours.

The following group of respondents had more neutral/mixed views on parental leave; these responses recognised strengths in the system but raised caveats or limitations:

- Gender imbalance in uptake: maternity leave is better supported or more visible than paternity leave.
- Unpaid extended leave is rare—usually due to economic disincentives.
- Part-time work options exist, but may carry stigma or negative career impact.
- Policy structure is clear, but some lack awareness or experience.

The group of respondents with negative/problematic experiences described following problems or challenges associated with parental leave:

- Lack of adequate coverage for employees on leave causes resentment and pressure on remaining staff.
- Return to work is difficult, with limited support and poor reintegration.
- Cultural bias remains—e.g. women seen as less productive after maternity leave, and men discouraged from taking full parental leave.
- Use of leave can harm internal promotion opportunities.

Several respondents stated they had no personal experience with parental leave or felt unable to comment meaningfully.

5.2.4 ELIXIR Culture and Climate - Gender Equality

Respondents were asked whether they could provide more insight into general aspects of culture and climate regarding gender equality in the ELIXIR environment. While around 50% of respondents agree or strongly agree that women and men are equally treated in ELIXIR, the remaining 50% of respondents' opinions were divided between disagreement (a very small portion of respondents strongly disagree), and indifference.

With regards to ELIXIR's commitment to promotion of gender equality, the majority of respondents (76% in total) agrees and strongly agrees with the statement.

The received assessments have been summaries in Table 3 below:

Table 3: Culture and climate regarding gender equality in ELIXIR

Question	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Agree	Strongly agree
In general, women and men are treated equally in ELIXIR	3%	24%	16%	31%	26%
ELIXIR is committed to promoting gender equality (especially in the framework of the events management Code of Conduct)	2%	7%	16%	48%	28%

Regarding respondent's age demographics, two groups of respondents have been identified: under and over 40 years old. The under-40 group has a majority of respondents in the 31-40 age range, while the over-40 group is mostly aged 41-60, with a small proportion of 61+ respondents (2). Under-40s are more likely to disagree (33%) with the statement on gender equality, whereas over-40s show higher agreement (65% combined agree/strongly agree). Furthermore, when asked about promotion of gender equality in ELIXIR, both age groups largely support ELIXIR's gender equality promotion. Over-40s are more likely to "strongly agree" (35%) compared to under-40s (19%).

Regarding the treatment of women and men in ELIXIR, the following results were obtained with gender filter applied:

- Male respondents are significantly more likely to believe that men and women are treated equally, with 94% agreement (Agree + Strongly Agree).
- Female respondents are more divided: only 44% agree or strongly agree, while 34% disagree or strongly disagree.
- 22% of females remain neutral, compared to none of the males.

Regarding the promotion of gender equality in ELIXIR, the following results were obtained with gender filter applied:

- All male respondents agreed (100%) that ELIXIR is committed to gender equality, with the majority (63%) strongly agreeing.
- Female agreement was slightly lower at 69%, with a significant portion remaining neutral (20%) or disagreeing (12%).

The following question explored respondents' perception of difference in the allocation of the following opportunities regarding their position in ELIXIR. When broken down with regards to age groups (under and over 40), the following results were obtained:

- Under-40 respondents are more likely to disagree that men and women are treated equally and to perceive more gender-based differences across organisational domains.
- Over-40 respondents express greater agreement with ELIXIR's gender equality efforts and rate gender treatment more positively overall.
- However, both age groups agree on areas like leadership representation as a domain with clear gender disparities.

Overall results are summarised in Table 4 below.

Table 4: Perceptions of allocation of opportunities in ELIXIR with regards to gender

Question	Mainly allocated to women	Often allocated to women	I have not noticed a difference	Often allocated to men	Mainly allocated to men	I don't have an opinion
Mentoring and/or other guidance in making career decisions	11%	28%	40%	7%	0%	14%
Representation in senior positions	2%	2%	21%	47%	24%	5%
Positive attention from, or additional time with, senior management	2%	7%	53%	16%	9%	14%
Access to informal circles of influence	0%	3%	33%	40%	12%	12%
Recruitment	0%	12%	59%	5%	2%	22%
Promotion	0%	5%	42%	25%	5%	23%
Formal training and career development opportunities	3%	10%	67%	5%	0%	14%
Invitations or opportunities (i.e. funding, additional time) to attend conferences, lectures, etc.	0%	5%	52%	22%	2%	19%
Recognition of intellectual contributions during meetings, conferences, workshops, etc.	0%	2%	53%	31%	2%	12%
Funds and monetary resources	0%	5%	59%	10%	2%	24%
Awards and recognition of excellence	2%	5%	47%	17%	5%	24%
Support in grant preparation and writing	0%	2%	70%	7%	2%	19%

When gender filter was applied to collected answers, the following results were obtained from 57 respondents, 16 male and 41 female, as presented in Table 4.1 below:

- Across every category, female respondents perceive significantly more gender-based disparities than male respondents.
- The most pronounced gaps are in promotion opportunities, platform allocation, and event representation.
- Male responses indicate minimal perception of inequality—no domain exceeds 6% for observed gender differences.

Table 4.1: Selected highlights regarding allocation perceptions of opportunities in ELIXIR with regards to gender, according to domain of interest

Question	Female: "I observe a difference"	Male: "I observe a difference"
Mentoring and/or other guidance in making career decisions	51%	31%
Representation in senior positions	83%	50%
Positive attention from, or additional time with, senior management	39%	12%
Access to informal circles of influence	71%	13%
Recruitment	19%	13%
Promotion	41%	13%
Formal training and career development opportunities	19%	19%
Invitations or opportunities (i.e. funding, additional time) to attend conferences, lectures, etc.	33%	19%
Recognition of intellectual contributions during meetings, conferences, workshops, etc.	41%	13%
Funds and monetary resources	14%	25%
Awards and recognition of excellence	32%	25%
Support in grant preparation and writing	16%	0%

The final question in the survey inquired about any other experiences or perceptions of gender bias (or lack thereof) in ELIXIR. In total we received 22 responses, categorised below from positive (no bias experienced) to negative (clear concerns or examples of bias).

Overall insight

While several respondents report no personal experience of gender bias, the majority of responses describe ongoing imbalances—especially in leadership visibility, speaker selection, and distribution of influence vs. workload between genders. There is a clear desire for more proactive and inclusive practices, especially around non-male leadership promotion and institution-wide engagement with gender equality efforts.

A group of respondents offered positive responses with no personal experience of gender bias in ELIXIR:

- Some noted equal or greater representation of women in their own teams or management structures.
- A few highlighted a lack of awareness of any inequality in their personal experience.

The following group of survey respondents offered more neutral perceptions regarding observation of gender bias in ELIXIR; they expressed ambivalent or nuanced views:

- Note that systemic or structural factors (e.g. maternity leave norms in some countries) affect gender participation more than ELIXIR-specific issues.
- Acknowledged that efforts are underway, but progress is uneven and long-term.
- Recognised that personal experience may not reflect broader realities.

Finally, the last group of respondents provided constructive criticism noting areas for further changes to be implemented. These responses highlighted gaps in representation or engagement, but framed them as opportunities for improvement:

- Called for more visible promotion of non-male leadership, especially at the Hub level and across platforms.
- Suggested better gender balance in event speakers and senior roles.
- Recommended more inclusive and compulsory gender bias discussions, not just for the already committed.

6. Conclusions

6.1 Conclusions from desk-analysis exercise

An analysis of participation data across 22 countries and institutions revealed a total of 309 individuals, with 108 identifying as female (35%) and 201 as male (65%). This overall distribution highlights a significant gender imbalance, with men comprising nearly two-thirds of the participant base.

At the country level, the representation of women varied widely. Countries such as Portugal (71%), Sweden (64%), and Estonia (56%) demonstrated strong female participation in leadership positions, suggesting positive local conditions or successful gender initiatives. In contrast, countries like the Czech Republic, Hungary, Slovenia, and Luxembourg reported female participation below 25%, indicating areas where targeted interventions may be needed.

Encouragingly, several countries approached gender parity, including France (47%), Greece (44%), Norway (44%), and the United Kingdom (42%). These could serve as models for best practices and peer learning. Meanwhile, countries with the largest total participation, such as Belgium and Czech Republic, also showed notable imbalances, underlining the need to address not just quantity but quality of gender inclusion.

An analysis of 259 individuals across various organisational roles revealed that 39% were female and 61% male, reflecting a modest improvement over the overall country-level balance.

Roles related to training and Node coordination show relatively strong female representation. For example, 58% of Training Coordinators (TrC) and 80% of Deputy Training Coordinators were women. The Legal role also had 67% female participation, while the Node Coordinator role had a balanced profile with 65% women. These roles may represent more inclusive pathways and could be leveraged to support women's career development within the network.

Conversely, technical and senior leadership roles show markedly lower female participation. Only 9% of Technical Coordinators (TeC) and 8% of Deputy TeCs were women. Roles such as Platform Lead and Head of Node included women at just 31%, while others like Data Stewardship Manager, Contract Administrator, and Research Office roles had no female representation at all. This indicates a concentration of women in support and mid-level functions, while men dominate highly technical or strategic positions.

6.2 Conclusions from 2025 survey of Equality, Diversity and Inclusion perceptions in ELIXIR

Progress on EDI

There are clear signs that ELIXIR's efforts toward equality, diversity and inclusion are making an impact, particularly regarding increased access to training and mentoring. There are positive perceptions of gender equality at events, as well as broader participation in ELIXIR structures and programmes. However, progress remains uneven across roles, career stages, and personal circumstances. Additionally, a significant majority of respondents to the survey were female, indicating their increased engagement in this area.

Structural barriers

Despite overall inclusivity, certain groups consistently report reduced access to opportunities, such as individuals with caring responsibilities, disabilities, or who are affected by parental leave often face limitations in engagement. Female respondents are more likely to be in parenting roles and to have primary or sole caregiving responsibility for children. Male respondents report more frequently that care responsibilities are equally shared or that they do not have the primary role. In addition, age and institutional constraints also emerged as common access barriers.

However, other barriers are considered equality hindering access to opportunities and professional development: workload, cost, and time pressure to name the biggest barriers. Across the board, respondents reported time pressure (67%) as the dominant barrier to engaging with ELIXIR activities. It is followed by costs (34%), location, and lack of institutional support. These challenges often outweigh any formal restrictions, highlighting the need for more flexible, well-communicated participation models.

Remote and flexible working arrangements

Flexible working arrangements have become critical for productivity, health, and work-life balance, particularly for carers and those with health conditions. Remote work is seen not just as a convenience, but as an enabler of full participation in ELIXIR, e.g. given the number of ELIXIR face-to-face meetings that are hybrid (Platforms, Communities, All Hands Meeting, etc.).

Gender Equality imbalances

While a majority see ELIXIR as committed to gender equality, a significant minority still perceive men as the ones dominating senior positions and informal influence networks. Recognition and access to resources remain skewed in some contexts. Men overwhelmingly perceive ELIXIR as equitable, both in terms of treatment and commitment to gender equality. Women report more mixed and critical views, with notable concern about disparities in advancement, visibility, and recognition. There is a marked divergence between how men and women experience or perceive ELIXIR's EDI environment. Finally, parental leave, particularly for men or extended/unpaid leave, is still culturally and structurally under-supported.

Communication gaps

Several respondents noted lack of clarity or visibility of opportunities as well as an overwhelming or poorly structured information provided. These issues reduce uptake of training, funding, and mentoring, especially for newcomers, early-career researchers, and those with limited time available.

Visual and cultural representation

While some are satisfied with ELIXIR's current visual communication, many expressed a desire for more visible inclusion of underrepresented groups (e.g. racial minorities, LGBTQ+, carers, early-career researchers), as well as a shift away from tokenism toward authentic, diverse storytelling.

Psychological safety

Despite many positive trends, only about half of respondents feel safe reporting EDI concerns. This indicates a trust gap that requires sustained attention to reporting mechanisms, leadership visibility and organisational culture and accountability.

7. Impact

The 2025 ELIXIR EDI survey provides a critical checkpoint against the goals set out in the ELIXIR Equal Opportunity Strategy. While there are encouraging signs—such as strong female representation at mid-career level and broad engagement with training opportunities, persistent structural and cultural barriers are slowing progress toward equality.

The table below maps the 2025 EDI survey findings against the strategic objectives set out in ELIXIR’s Equal Opportunity Strategy. It highlights areas of identified challenges, related recommendations mapped against those challenges and gaps where further action is needed to increase existing benchmarks and meet the targeted values set by ELIXIR’s Equal Opportunity Strategy by year 2. A full list of recommendations from ELIXIR Equal Opportunity Strategy can be found in the Annex to this deliverable.

Table 5: Measuring impact: benchmarking ELIXIR Equal Opportunities Strategy to EDI survey results

Challenge in ELIXIR Equal Opportunity Strategy	Recommendations from ELIXIR Equal Opportunity Strategy	EDI survey benchmark	Impact measure
<p>Underrepresentation and Systemic Bias</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Women and minority groups underrepresented in senior roles • Gender imbalance in STEM • “Leaky pipeline” effects 	<p>4. Encourage national bodies to consider balance in appointments (e.g. ELIXIR Board, HoN)</p> <p>5. Enforce diversity in ELIXIR-appointed governance groups.</p> <p>13. Promote diversity in grant work-package leadership roles</p>	<p>Desk Analysis (5.1) Leadership Roles Gender Gap:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Women comprise 35% of ELIXIR participants (overall) • 31% of Heads of Node are women • 31% of Platform Leads are women • 38% of Chiefs of Staff are women 	<p>Reduce Overall Gender Imbalance</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Achieve ≥40% female participation across all roles by end of Year 2 (currently 35%) • Annual increase of ≥2.5 pp % female of total participants • Analyse participation data by gender/Node • Follow up with Nodes showing no improvement vs. prior cycle <p>Ongoing: Update gender data bi-annually (Node Coordinator and ELIXIR Head of Operations)</p>

<p>Institutional and Cultural Barriers</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Implicit bias in recruitment and promotion • Lack of flexible work and childcare • Microaggression, discriminatory cultures 	<p>2. Review recruitment practices to eliminate bias</p> <p>3. Align employment terms with principles of organisations Equal Opportunities Policy.</p> <p>6. Ensure diversity in speakers, session chairs, committees and trainers at ELIXIR events</p> <p>8. Broaden and diversify participation across Hub, Nodes, Platforms and Communities in leadership, events and staff exchanges.</p>	<p>Desk Analysis (5.1)</p> <p>Cultural Representation Imbalances:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gender balance varies widely by country • Countries with <30% female engagement: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Slovenia (20%), ○ Hungary & Czech Republic (21%), ○ Luxembourg (22%) ○ Israel (25%) 	<p>Address Country-Level Disparities</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Raise female participation to $\geq 30\%$ in under-25% countries • Cut number of <25% countries by half by Year 2 • Generate Node country profiles • Bilateral check-ins with underperformers • Showcase exemplary Nodes (e.g. Portugal, Sweden, Estonia) <p>Ongoing: Targeted follow-up after each report (ELIXIR Diversity Leads: Heads of Node and Hub Head of Operations)</p> <p>Track & Mitigate Gender Clustering in Functional Silos</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reduce roles with 0% female presence to zero (e.g. Data Steward, Contract Admin) • Track shifts in female presence in previously male-only roles • Conduct qualitative follow-up for persistent gaps
<p>Inequality in Research Funding</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Grant success disparities • Biased peer review 	<p>13. Promote diversity in grant work-package leadership roles</p>	<p>Desk Analysis (5.1)</p> <p>Strategic Role Disparities¹⁰:</p> <p>Women underrepresented in funding-influencing roles:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Only 9% of Technical Coordinators (TeC) • 8% of Deputy TeCs are women 	<p>Tracking grant awards by demographics; monitoring co-leadership diversity</p> <p>Improve Female Representation in Technical & Leadership Roles:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Double TeC from 9% → 18% • Double Deputy TeC from 8% → 16% in 2 years • Increase % of women in technical/strategic roles • Bi-annually track new female appointments

¹⁰ NB: these roles are not equally represented across ELIXIR Nodes.

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 0% in Data Stewardship Manager and Research Office roles 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Compare with prior cycles Conduct interviews/focus groups on leadership barriers
<p>Lack of Robust Monitoring and Accountability</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Inconsistent diversity data Policies unevaluated for impact 	<p>1. Each organisation affiliated to ELIXIR has its own institutional Equal Opportunities Policy.</p> <p>9. Collect and report diversity data on applicants and staff annually.</p> <p>10. Collect diversity data on speakers, instructors, attendees, programme committee members and session chairs at ELIXIR events.</p> <p>11. Ensure GDPR-compliant data use for collection of personal data.</p>	<p>Desk Analysis (5.1)</p> <p>Gender Balance Monitoring Gaps Identified</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Gender balance across roles still below parity (avg. 39% female role-holders) Lack of full gender-disaggregated data for event participation or hiring cycles 	<p>Ongoing Monitoring Mechanism</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Collect gender-disaggregated data by Node and role every 2 years Publish annual visual dashboards Present findings at HoN/Board meetings (ELIXIR Director) Assign actions to Nodes below thresholds
<p>Intersectionality Often Overlooked</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Compound disadvantage not addressed in policy 	<p>10. Consider multiple characteristics when collecting diversity data of speakers and participants events</p> <p>12. Benchmark equality data against national charter schemes, such as Athena SWAN, Race Equality Charter</p>	<p>EDI Perceptions Survey (5.2)</p> <p>Survey Participant Diversity:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 71% identified as women, 2% non-binary Variation in age, with 34% aged 30-40, 31% aged 41-50 	<p>Increase future EDI Perceptions survey participation amongst males from 28% → ≥40%</p>

<p>Accessibility Gaps</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Barriers for people with disabilities in tools/events 	<p>7. Ensure online tools meet accessibility standards.</p> <p>10. Ensure events are fully accessible to people with disabilities.</p>	<p>EDI Perceptions Survey (5.2)</p> <p>The survey does not capture disability statistics, revealing a gap in accessibility benchmarking.</p>	<p>Compliance with W3C standards; attendee feedback on accessibility.</p>
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The 2025 ELIXIR EDI survey reflects continued progress toward a more inclusive and equitable research infrastructure, yet several critical benchmarks outlined in the ELIXIR Equal Opportunity Strategy remain unmet. While participation of women in ELIXIR overall stands at 35%, this still falls short of the 40% target. Representation in leadership and strategic roles—such as Heads of Node, Platform Leads, and Technical Coordinators, remains disproportionately low for women, with little improvement from prior cycles. Country-level disparities persist, with multiple Nodes (e.g. Slovenia, Hungary, Czech Republic) showing <25% female engagement. Gender clustering is evident in certain functions and intersectional factors such as caregiving, disability, and age continue to impact access.

To meet 2027 targets, ELIXIR must accelerate efforts in strategic role diversification, improve data monitoring at Node and role level, and embed intersectionality into all policy, funding, and event practices. Coordinated, data-driven follow-up with underperforming Nodes will be essential to achieving system-wide progress.

8. Recommendations

Based on the 2025 benchmarking analysis, ELIXIR must reinforce accountability at Node level, improve gender and role-disaggregated monitoring, and strengthen leadership diversity. A shift from awareness to sustained structural change is needed to achieve parity, inclusion, and long-term cultural transformation across the ELIXIR community.

The following recommendations highlight priority areas for action to align more closely with ELIXIR's Equal Opportunity Strategy. These focus on improving accountability, and ensuring that progress is measurable, inclusive, and sustainable across the ELIXIR community. For close monitoring of improvements, the overall recommendation is to repeat the survey bi-annually.

1. Reduce overall gender imbalance across ELIXIR

Achieve at least 40% female participation in ELIXIR-affiliated roles by end of 2027 and female representation \geq 40% across all roles (currently 35%). More specifically, it is recommended to achieve:

- A year-on-year increase of \geq 2.5 percentage points and % female of total active participants;
- Monitor gender ratio trends across Nodes and functions and provide participation databases (disaggregated by gender and Node);
- Compare against previous cycle's data; flag Nodes with no improvement.

2. Address country-level gender disparities

Raise female participation to \geq 30% in countries currently below 25% (e.g. Czech Republic, Hungary, Slovenia, Luxembourg) as well as % of female participants per Node/country. In particular:

- Number of countries under the 25% threshold to be reduced by half by end of 2027;
- Identify priority countries for support and generate country profiles;
- Hold bilateral check-ins with underperforming Nodes;
- Highlight exemplary Nodes (e.g. Portugal, Sweden, Estonia) for best practice sharing.

3. Improve female representation in technical and leadership roles

Double female representation in Technical Coordinator roles from 9% to 18%, and in Deputy roles from 8% to 16% within 2 years as well as % of women in Technical Coordinator, Deputy Technical Coordinator, and Platform Lead roles:

- Provide gender breakdown in all senior technical/strategic roles and gender-disaggregated role data (technical & leadership);
- Track % of newly appointed female leaders in each cycle (bi-annually);
- Compare with prior periods; assess trends and turnover.
- Identify survey barriers to leadership roles through interviews or focus groups |

4. Sustain and leverage strong female participation in mid-level and coordination roles

Maintain or exceed current levels in roles with $\geq 50\%$ female participation as well as % of women in Training Coordinators and Legal roles:

- Career progression of women in these tracks; monitor promotion rates or transitions into senior roles;
- Monitor retention rates in these functions as well as career transitions from mid-level to senior roles;
- Identify development opportunities, as well as obstacles to progression, and create progression pathways.

5. Increase gender parity in high-participation Nodes

Ensure countries with high total participation (e.g. Belgium, Czech Republic) meet at least 35% female representation | - % female in high-volume Nodes:

- Monitor gender parity index (female/male ratio) by size of Node and proportion of countries with large participation and $< 30\%$ women;
- Make annual Node-specific improvement plans; tag top 5 most populous Nodes;
- Request annual improvement actions from those below target;
- Showcase results of proactive Nodes in bi-annual dashboard.

6. Track and mitigate gender concentration in functional silos

Broaden distribution of female talent across all roles to avoid clustering in only support/coordinator roles as well as % of female representation in each functional group:

- Number of roles with 0% female representation reduced to 0; provide role-based gender analysis;
- Number of roles with "no female presence" reduced to 0; track shifts in female entry to previously male-only roles;
- Encourage nominations or targeted development in those gaps;
- Include qualitative follow-up where roles remain exclusively male.

Proposal for actioning activities with continuous monitoring and reporting mechanism can be found in the Table 7 below:

Action	Frequency	Owner
Update gender disaggregated data by role and country	Every other year	Node HR reps + ELIXIR Hub
Conduct targeted follow-up with Nodes below threshold	After each report	ELIXIR Head of Operations/Hub Diversity Lead
Present findings at Heads of Nodes and Board meetings	Annually	ELIXIR Director or Delegate
Publish high-level visual summaries for transparency	Annually	Hub Communications Team

Suggested Indicators for report template

- % female participants (overall)
- % female participation per country
- % female by role group (coordination, leadership, technical)
- Roles with 0% female representation
- New appointments: % female
- Countries below 25% female participation
- Progress on targets set in last cycle

9. Deviation from Description of Action

Not applicable

Annexes

Annex 1. List of Recommendations from ELIXIR Equal Opportunity Strategy¹¹

1. Each of the organisations that form part of the ELIXIR infrastructure are recommended to have their own institutional Equal Opportunities Policy.
2. ELIXIR organisations should review recruitment processes to eliminate the impact of unconscious bias, for example by following the recommendations in the LIBRA Handbook¹².
3. ELIXIR organisations should review the principles of their institutional Equal Opportunities Policy and ensure that these are upheld within their terms and conditions of employment.
4. ELIXIR strongly recommends that the balance of gender, ethnicity and other under-represented groups is taken into consideration by national bodies when appointing members to decision making bodies, such as the ELIXIR Board and Heads of Nodes Committee, and actively seek to develop a diverse cadre of staff when succession planning for future appointments.
5. For governance groups appointed by the ELIXIR Board (SAB, IAC) and other working groups, ELIXIR can, and does, enforce consideration of balance and under-representation during the appointment process.
6. Organisers of training and events relating to ELIXIR should ensure that speakers and participants are diverse and include a representative balance with regard to gender, ethnicity, race, age, disability and sexuality, for example. This should include invited speakers, session chairs, committees and training staff, in order to increase the visibility of women and other under-represented groups at all stages of scientific careers.
7. ELIXIR online tools and services should aim to comply with industry accessibility standards, such as the W3C standards² in order to ensure that they are fully accessible to people with disabilities.
8. ELIXIR Hub, Nodes and Platforms should work with the ELIXIR Communities and the Use Cases to broaden and diversify participation in leadership, events and staff exchanges.
9. ELIXIR organisations are recommended to collect diversity data on applicants to their organisations, their staff and users on an annual basis in order to monitor the impact of diversity actions. This data should be reported to the ELIXIR Hub as part of an annual reporting process, which will monitor the trends

¹¹ Gater C. ELIXIR Equal Opportunities Strategy [version 1; not peer reviewed]. F1000Research 2018, 7(ELIXIR):1234 (document) (<https://doi.org/10.7490/f1000research.1115874.1>)

¹² https://www.eu-libra.eu/sites/default/files/article-files/libra_recruitment_guidelines_second_edition_0.pdf

10. Events organised within ELIXIR, such as training events, conferences and large meetings should collect diversity data on speakers, instructors, attendees, programme committee members and session chairs. Events should also be fully accessible to people with disabilities.
11. Data collection and processing by ELIXIR organisations must be compliant with the General Data Protection Regulation (2018) when personal data is included.
12. ELIXIR organisations are recommended to consider benchmarking their diversity activities within national charter schemes, such as the Athena Swan Charter and Race Equality Charter in the UK.
13. ELIXIR grants should consider diversity in work package leadership, including co-leadership as a development opportunity and consider equal opportunities in all aspects of the grant.
14. An Equal Opportunities Toolkit will be developed and ELIXIR organisations are recommended to draw from this and other resources.

Annex 2. Equality, Diversity and Inclusion perceptions in ELIXIR Survey Questions

Perceptions of Equality, Diversity and Inclusion (EDI) in ELIXIR

This ELIXIR survey includes questions adapted from the Gender Equality Audit and Monitoring (GEAM) tool, available under the following address: <https://geamtool.eu/manual>

This survey seeks your insight on equality and representation across the ELIXIR network. In particular, we ask for your feedback on issues that may impact gender equality. Additionally, we wish to understand equality in the broader context of socio-demographic and identity factors such as, for example, age, ethnicity, marital status and religion.

Alongside desk analysis of ELIXIR roles, the survey is being conducted as part of the [ELIXIR STEERS project](#). It will inform the deliverable D1.5 describing an ELIXIR Gender Equality Strategy addressing the Horizon Europe Gender Equality Plan (GEP) requirements and EC gender dimensions considerations, and provides a framework for adopting these within the ELIXIR network.

Before filling in this survey please read our [privacy statement](#). Your individual responses will not be directly identifiable in any reporting. Data will be handled in a way that protects your privacy, and only aggregated or de-identified information will be shared. While we cannot guarantee full anonymity due to technical limitations, we are committed to ensuring your responses are treated confidentially and respectfully.

Procedure

There are 20 questions in this survey and it shouldn't take more than 20 minutes to complete.

The survey consists of several parts related to different topics. You are kindly asked to answer as many questions as you can. Answers are saved automatically each time you click on Next in the online-survey interface. You can interrupt the survey any moment by clicking Save and finish later at the bottom top of each survey page. You will then be provided with a bookmark URL that can be copied to your clipboard, or emailed, to come back at a later point in time for final submission. **The resume link is for your personal use and should not be shared more widely.**

Thank you for taking part.

About you

These questions will help us understand if perceptions of equality, diversity and inclusion vary across different social groups.

1. Age *

- 21-30
- 31-40
- 41-50
- 51-60
- 61+
- Prefer not to say

2. Please indicate your gender identity. Are you: *

- Female
- Male
- Non-binary
- Prefer not to say
- Prefer to self-identify as: (please specify)

About your current position

Please provide details about your institutional role alongside your participation within ELIXIR.

3. What categories best describe the focus of your current role within your institute?

[Multiple selections allowed] *

- Bioinformatics
- Data management
- Communications
- Community manager
- External relations
- IT operations
- Legal / ethics professionals
- Operations/Administration/HR
- Project management
- Research technician
- Software development
- Training
- Other (please specify)

4. What seniority is your current institutional position? *

- Senior positions (e.g. Director, Associate/Full Professor)
- Middle career (e.g. Manager/Team leader/ Assistant Professor)
- Early career (e.g. officer/technician, PhD candidate, Post-doc)
- Intern
- Other (please specify)

5. What ELIXIR activities are you currently involved in? [Multiple selections allowed] *

- Commissioned Services
- EC projects
- Communities
- Platforms

- Focus Groups
- Governance and coordination of Node
- None at present
- Other (please specify)

6. Do you feel your participation in ELIXIR helped or hindered your career progression in any way?

7. Please indicate which, if any, of the following training or development resources provided directly or indirectly by ELIXIR you have accessed *

- ELIXIR Staff Exchange Programme
- ELIXIR Travel Grant
- ELIXIR Knowledge Exchange Programme
- ELIXIR governance and flagship (All Hands, Biohackathon) meetings
- Mentoring opportunities (e.g. ELEAD)
- Training courses, including self-paced, hybrid and in-person (e.g. Train-the-Trainer)
- Knowledge exchange clubs (e.g. TeSS club)
- Conferences and other events
- None of the above
- Other (please specify)

8. Do you consider the following criteria to be a barrier to accessing ELIXIR opportunities and activities: *

- Time pressure
- Cost
- A long-term health condition or disability
- Training doesn't meet my needs

- Location
- Parenting/caring responsibilities
- Language
- Lack of management support
- None of the above
- Other (please specify)

Perceptions on Equality, Diversity and Inclusion

We would like to better understand how various socio-demographic factors may influence equity and access within ELIXIR. Please indicate if any of the following factors appear to affect equitable access to opportunities in your ELIXIR-related work or environment.

9. In your opinion, do any characteristics listed below influence equal access or opportunity within ELIXIR, for example;
to be appointed in ELIXIR role at your institution
to access training, knowledge exchange or mentoring provided by ELIXIR
the possibility to receive funding to support ELIXIR activities *

Age

- Yes
 No
 Sometimes
 Not sure

Caring responsibilities

- Yes
 No
 Sometimes
 Not sure

Disability

- Yes
 No
 Sometimes
 Not sure

Ethnicity

- Yes
 No
 Sometimes
 Not sure

Gender identity

- Yes
 No
 Sometimes

Not sure

Marital or partnership status

- Yes
- No
- Sometimes
- Not sure

Nationality

- Yes
- No
- Sometimes
- Not sure

Pregnancy, maternity and parental leave

- Yes
- No
- Sometimes
- Not sure

Race

- Yes
- No
- Sometimes
- Not sure

Religion or belief

- Yes
- No
- Sometimes
- Not sure

Sex (biological)

- Yes
- No
- Sometimes
- Not sure

Sexual orientation

- Yes
- No
- Sometimes
- Not sure

Socio-economic background

- Yes
- No
- Sometimes
- Not sure

Trans identity/history

- Yes
- No
- Sometimes
- Not sure

10. In your opinion, do any characteristics listed need to be better represented in ELIXIR visual communications?

Caring Responsibilities

11. Are you the primary carer or assistant for an adult requiring care? *

- Yes
- No
- Prefer not to say

12. Are you the parent or legal guardian of any children below 18 years old? *

- Yes
- No
- Prefer not to say

13. Do you share the care responsibilities with another adult, and in what capacity? *

- No - I am single parent / legal guardian
- Yes - care responsibilities are equally shared
- Yes - I am primarily responsible
- Yes - I do not have primary responsibility

Flexible / remote working

Please reply considering your experience regarding flexible work arrangements at your current workplace over the last 12 months.

14. I worked from home or other places that were not my office *

- Yes - I exclusively work remotely
- Yes - hybrid working arrangement
- No
- Prefer not to say

15. If YES: I worked outside of the office because... [Multiple selections allowed] *

- I could concentrate better at home
- I needed to work outside office hours
- It was easier to take care of my children
- It was easier to take care of relatives/friends
- It was easier to deal with my domestic duties
- It was easier to deal with my social commitments or leisure activities
- I am fully remote
- It was requested by my employer
- Other (please specify)

Parental Leave

16. Considering the last 5 years, have you taken or are you currently taking any form or parental leave? Parental leave includes maternity leave, paternity leave, adoption leave, unpaid- or paid parental leave. *

- Yes
- No
- Prefer not to say

17. Please describe your perceptions of the uptake and use of parental leave options and resources, such as working part-time or taking extended unpaid parental leave, in your organisation.

ELIXIR Culture and Climate - Gender Equality

18. To what extent would you agree with the following statements: *

In general, women and men are treated equally in ELIXIR

- Strongly disagree
- Disagree
- Neither agree nor disagree
- Agree
- Strongly agree

ELIXIR is committed to promoting gender equality (especially in the framework of the events management Code of Conduct)

- Strongly disagree
- Disagree
- Neither agree nor disagree
- Agree
- Strongly agree

19. Do you perceive a difference in the allocation of the following regarding your position in ELIXIR? *

Mentoring and/or other guidance in making career decisions

- Mainly allocated to women
- Often allocation to women
- I have not noticed a difference
- Often allocated to men
- Mainly allocated to men
- I don't have an opinion

Representation in senior positions

- Mainly allocated to women
- Often allocation to women
- I have not noticed a difference
- Often allocated to men
- Mainly allocated to men
- I don't have an opinion

Positive attention from, or additional time with, senior management

- Mainly allocated to women

- Often allocation to women
- I have not noticed a difference
- Often allocated to men
- Mainly allocated to men
- I don't have an opinion

Access to informal circles of influence

- Mainly allocated to women
- Often allocation to women
- I have not noticed a difference
- Often allocated to men
- Mainly allocated to men
- I don't have an opinion

Recruitment

- Mainly allocated to women
- Often allocation to women
- I have not noticed a difference
- Often allocated to men
- Mainly allocated to men
- I don't have an opinion

Promotion

- Mainly allocated to women
- Often allocation to women
- I have not noticed a difference
- Often allocated to men
- Mainly allocated to men
- I don't have an opinion

Formal training and career development opportunities

- Mainly allocated to women
- Often allocation to women
- I have not noticed a difference
- Often allocated to men
- Mainly allocated to men
- I don't have an opinion

Invitations or opportunities (i.e. funding, additional time) to attend conferences, lectures, etc.

- Mainly allocated to women
- Often allocation to women
- I have not noticed a difference
- Often allocated to men
- Mainly allocated to men
- I don't have an opinion

Recognition of intellectual contributions during meetings, conferences, workshops, etc.

- Mainly allocated to women
- Often allocation to women
- I have not noticed a difference
- Often allocated to men
- Mainly allocated to men
- I don't have an opinion

Funds and monetary resources

- Mainly allocated to women
- Often allocation to women
- I have not noticed a difference
- Often allocated to men
- Mainly allocated to men
- I don't have an opinion

Awards and recognition of excellence

- Mainly allocated to women
- Often allocation to women
- I have not noticed a difference
- Often allocated to men
- Mainly allocated to men
- I don't have an opinion

Support in grant preparation and writing

- Mainly allocated to women
- Often allocation to women
- I have not noticed a difference
- Often allocated to men
- Mainly allocated to men
- I don't have an opinion

20. If you would like to tell us about your experiences or perceptions of gender bias (or lack thereof) please do so here.